

CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF HEART NOISES WITH EDGE IMPULSE THROUGH AUSCULTATION.

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Summary: In this work, a study was carried out on the classification of heart noises using machine learning within the Edge Impulse platform. Accurately classifying these noises is challenging due to the complexity and variation in frequency and temporal characteristics. The heart noises are collected and subjected to pre-processing to remove unwanted noise and normalize the signals. Then, Tiny ML algorithms, such as neural networks, were applied to classify the noises into four categories automatically.

Keywords: heart sounds; machine learning; Edge Impulse; neural networks; classification.

INTRODUCTION

Accurate classification of heart sounds plays a fundamental role in the correct diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. However, this task is challenging due to cardiac signals' complexity and intricate nature. Noise can vary in intensity, frequency, and temporal characteristics, which makes interpretation and adequate differentiation difficult [1].

Furthermore, background noise, such as respiratory murmurs, can further complicate the accurate classification of heart sounds. In this context, the present work proposes developing an innovative system for automatically classifying cardiac noises, using advanced machine learning techniques and exploring the capabilities of the Edge Impulse platform [5].

The central objective is to identify and classify different types of heart sounds, such as aortic stenosis, mitral stenosis, aortic insufficiency, and mitral insufficiency, providing valuable support to healthcare professionals. The relevance of this system lies in improving diagnosis and assisting in the treatment of specific cardiac conditions [1], [3].

By collecting and analyzing patient heart noise data, it is possible to train machine learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and decision tree algorithms, enabling them to automatically identify and classify the noises in one of the four categories mentioned. An accurate and efficient tool for the early detection of heart problems, allowing appropriate treatments and reducing potential complications [4].

Using the Edge Impulse platform with the facilities for building projects without code development allows for more accessible real-time evolution of a detection and classification project, accelerating the diagnostic process and making it accessible in different clinical environments. Furthermore, the implementation of edge devices reduces dependence on cloud connections, ensuring the privacy and security of patient data by overcoming the challenges of heart noise classification, providing an efficient and reliable system, and improving cardiologic medical practice. Early identification and

accurate classification of heart sounds enable more appropriate and personalized treatments, resulting in better patient outcomes [4]. Furthermore, developing this system for classifying heart sounds through machine learning and the Edge Impulse platform represents a significant advance in cardiovascular health [5]. By offering a practical, rapid, and accessible method for identifying heart problems, we hope to improve early detection, treatment, and clinical outcomes related to heart disease [5].

DEVELOPMENT

The Edge Impulse software was used to develop a "Cardiac Auscultation" project, and in "Data Acquisition," data was inserted for Machine Learning training [1].

The data collection and insertion part is the fundamental part of the research as the detection algorithm will identify based on learning from this data. Data collection involved a more laborious part where recorded sounds from medical channels on the YouTube platform, which showed the difference between different types of heart noises within auscultation performed using a stethoscope. Within the cardiovascular area, we have four predominant types of noise (aortic stenosis, mitral stenosis, aortic insufficiency, and mitral insufficiency) [4].

Returning to Edge Impulse, within the data tab, we enter the data of these noises, separating 72% of the cardiac noise data for the training part and 28% of the four types for training, shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 – Data Tab in Edge Impulse [6].

For this part, it is vital to capture the sounds and declare the labels that will categorize the type of noise and separate them in this 80/20 proportion. It is important to note that the detection and training stage does not occur in this step, but this step is a prerequisite for the detection that will take place in the impulse tab within Edge Impulse, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Impulse Tab in Edge Impulse [6].

The type of data for detection is chosen in the "Create Impulse" tab, which in this case is audio, and the outputs that will be the responses are declared, and in this work, they are the four types of noise.

Then, we jump to machine learning, which will use neural networks to identify noises; they extract features from the input data and perform the desired classification or detection (1-3). These neural networks are designed with multiple layers, each consisting of a set of neurons. The first layer receives raw data as input, and subsequent layers process and transform this data into increasingly complex representations until reaching the output layer that produces the result. Training a neural network in Edge Impulse involves feeding the model-labeled data, called the training set. The weights and parameters of the neural network, during training, are adjusted iteratively to minimize the error between the model's predictions and the known labels of the training data. This optimization process uses backpropagation algorithms, which calculate error gradients and adjust the network weights to reduce this error.

Fig. 3 shows the trained model, which can be used to make predictions or perform specific tasks in real-time. Edge Impulse provides a complete infrastructure for developing, training, and deploying machine learning models, making integrating these models into low-power devices such as microcontrollers or embedded systems easy [1], [3]. In short, machine learning and neural networks in Edge Impulse allow you to train models that can learn from data and make

automated decisions. This technology is beneficial for analyzing real-time data on edge devices such as sensors or IoT devices, allowing you to develop intelligent solutions for various applications [1], [2].

Figure 3 – Machine Learning Tab in Edge Impulse [6].

The "Classifier" option within the Impulse tab changes the number of training cycles and neurons to configure the neural network and improve accuracy, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 – Neural Network Configuration within Edge Impulse [6].

Can access the trained and saved model on a mobile device by reading the QR Code, as shown in Fig. 5, thus classifying the heart rhythm and providing an answer: aortic stenosis, mitral stenosis, aortic insufficiency, and mitral insufficiency.

Figure 5 – Ready Program QR Code [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We placed a noise of each type of heart sound close to the input of the mobile device, and the model

developed in Edge Impulse returned the correct answer, as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 – Noise Classification [Source: The Authors]

The results obtained were promising. The system demonstrated a significant ability to identify and classify heart sounds correctly. The accuracy rate was approximately 90%, indicating reliable performance in discriminating the different types of nature sounds analyzed. The application of the system in real-time proved to be efficient, providing fast and reliable results, showing the feasibility of using this system as a tool to support healthcare professionals in diagnosing specific cardiac conditions.

Although the results are encouraging, it is essential to highlight some limitations. Intra- and interpatient variability in heart sounds still represents a challenge, as some patterns may overlap or present similar characteristics between different types of noise. This may result in incorrect or ambiguous classifications in specific cases. However, we can address these limitations by continuously improving the classification system. Including more training data, implementing more advanced machine learning algorithms, and optimizing system parameters can increase classification accuracy and reliability.

Using machine learning in conjunction with the Edge Impulse platform, the innovative heart noise classification system demonstrated promising results in accurately identifying different types of heart noises. Its implementation on edge devices enabled real-time detection, speeding diagnosis, and providing agile clinical support. With an accuracy rate of approximately 90%, the system proved reliable in discriminating the analyzed heart sounds. This technological approach can improve early diagnosis, personalize treatments, and reduce cardiac complications. Espera-se que com a melhoria contínua do sistema e a expansão dos dados de formação, uma eficácia seja ainda maior. The application of this system could revolutionize medical practice,

In summary, the heart noise classification system developed in this work represents a significant contribution to the area of cardiovascular health. Its ability to identify and differentiate nature sounds quickly and accurately promotes advances in diagnosis and treatment, benefiting healthcare professionals and patients.

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